

susceptible; 5, resistant; and 3, moderately resistant. Results indicated that the Pattambi BPH population is likely to be less virulent than that at Raipur or Hyderabad. □

Evaluating rice cultivars for yellow stem borer (YSB) resistance

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Forty-one rice cultivars were screened for field resistance to YSB during 1988 at the Rice Research Station, Tirur, India.

Seedlings (30-d-old) for each entry were spaced at 20 × 10 cm in three 4-m rows in a randomized block design with three replications. Susceptible check Jaya was planted in single rows between entries in each replication and in three rows between replications.

Deadheart was counted 15, 30, and 45 d after transplanting (DT) and whitehead at 10 d before harvest for 20 randomly selected hills for each entry. Infestation was scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES).

W1263 was resistant at 15 DT and moderately resistant at other times. TM8089, TM2011, and CO 43 were moderately susceptible at 15 and 30 DT. TKM9 was moderately susceptible at all times (see table). □

Field reaction^a of rice varieties to YSB under natural infestation, Tirur, India, 1988.

Accession	Parentage	Deadheart score ^b			Whitehead score 10 d before harvest
		15 DT	30 DT	45 DT	
TM8089	Selffrom TKM9	5	5	7	9
TM2011	C22/TKM6/TR50	5	5	7	9
TM4640	BAM3/IR50	5	7	7	9
TM4309	BAM3/IR50	5	7	7	7
TPS1	IR8/Kattaisamba	7	7	7	9
PMK1	CO 25/ADT31	7	7	7	9
IET7511	Ras/Barket	7	7	7	9
TKM9	TKM7/IR8	5	5	5	5
ADT37	BG280-2/PTB33	7	7	7	9
TM6012	C22/BJ1	7	7	7	3
TM5656	IR50/TKM9	7	7	7	9
TM5118	BAM3/IR50	7	7	7	9
TM10232	TKM6/IET1444	7	7	7	9
TM1086	Ponni/ME80	5	7	7	7
TM5670	IR50/TKM9	7	7	7	9
TM4937	BAM3/IR50	7	7	7	9
TM4955	BAM3/IR50	7	7	7	9
TM4865	AC76/TKM8	7	7	7	9
TM8601	TKM9/ADT9/CR141/IR26	7	7	7	9
TM8381	IR262/CR1106-190	7	7	7	7
TM8602	CO 31/22	7	7	7	9
TM4300	IR262/Bhavani	7	7	7	9
TMA1087	Ponni/CH1039	7	7	7	7
TNAU891434	IET6262/TBAY1756	5	7	7	9
TNAU840337	TKM9/White Ponni	5	7	7	9
TNAU6790/2	BAM3/TN1	7	7	7	9
TNAU6540/2	GMR2/BAM3	7	7	7	7
TNAU843062	IET4141/CO43	5	7	7	9
PM1381	IR13564-149-3/ASD4	7	7	7	7
PM1340	IR13564/ASD4	7	7	7	7
MW10	MTU15/Yaikyakunantoku	7	7	7	9
AS26556	IET5233/IR2153-26-3-5-2	5	7	7	9
ACM38	ASD4/TKM6	9	7	9	9
CO 11	GEB24/ <i>O. perennis</i>	7	7	7	7
IR20	IR262/CR106-190	7	7	7	5
ADT38	IR1529/IR4432/IR7963	5	7	7	9
CO 43	Daral/IR20	5	5	7	9
ADT39	IR8/IR20	7	7	7	9
White Ponni	Tg 65/ME80	7	7	7	7
W1263	MTU15/Eswarakora	1	3	3	3
Jaya	TN1/T14	9	9	9	9

^aDeadheart and whitehead scores by SES. ^bDT = days after transplanting.

Field reaction of rice breeding lines to brown planthopper (BPH) in Pondicherry, India

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BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) is an important pest in Pondicherry region, especially in sornavari season (May to Aug/Sep). During 1988 and 1989 wet seasons (Jun-Sep) 143 entries of advanced rice breeding lines (including local susceptible and resistant checks) From the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, were screened in the field against BPH.

Field reaction of selected breeding lines to BPH in Pondicherry, India, 1988 and 1989 wet seasons.

Designation	Cross	BPH damage score ^a			Reaction to other pests ^b
		1988	1989	Mean	
BPT2217	BPT3291/ARC6650	3	1	2	—
BPT4363	BPT3291/Velluthacheera	3	1	2	—
BPT4365	BPT3291/Velluthacheera	3	1	2	—
RP1579-13-11-12	Phalguna/ARC6650	5	3	4	RTV-P
RP1746-1723-8	RPA5824/RP79-9//Rasi//PTB21	3	3	3	LF-S
RP2332-16-3	Ratna/ARC10654	3	3	3	LF-S
RP2332-18-15	Ratna/ARC10654	3	3	3	LF-S
RP2332-19-9-6	Ratna/ARC10654	3	3	3	—
RP2362-227-22	Nagarjuna/ARC5989	3	3	3	—
RP2542-1657-194	Swarnadhan/RP1579-37	3	3	3	—
RP2.543-1444-46	Rasi/RP1579-38	3	3	3	—
RP2.543-1464-152	Rasi/RP1579-38	3	3	3	—
RP2547-985-100	RP2205/RP1579-38	5	5	5	—
RP2547-1059-118	RP2205/RP1579-38	5	5	5	—
IR50 (local susceptible check)	—	9	9	9	—
ADT36 (local check)	—	3	3	3	—
PY3 (local resistant check)	—	1	3	2	LF-S
TN1 (standard susceptible check)	—	9	9	9	—

^aBy the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. ^bRTV-P = rice tungro virus present, LF-S = leafhopper susceptible.